

"Boosting Sustainable Tourism Development and Capacity of Tourism SMEs through Transnational Cooperation and Knowledge Transfer"

GRO/SME/19/C/077 (COS-TOURCOOP-2019-3-01)

Project Logo:

Name of the Project: Improving sustainability of tourism SMEs through knowledge transfer, international cooperation and multi-stakeholder engagement

Acronym of the Project: TOURISME

Proposal Number of the Project: 951103

Project Duration and start date: 33 months, 16th September 2020

Lead partner/coordinator:

1. Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation S.L / CE (Spain)

Partners:

2. Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias, S.A. / ITC (Spain)

3. Association Des Villes Et Regions Pour La Gestion Durable Des Ressources / ACR+ (Belgium)

4. Regione Autonoma Della Sardegna / RAS (Italy)

5. Sistemi Formativi Confindustria SCPA / SFC (Italy)

6. Scuola Superiore Di Studi Universitari E Di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna / SSSA (Italy)

7. Institut D'aménagement Et D'urbanisme De La Region D'Île De France / L'InstParisReg (France)

8. Nicosia Development Agency LTD / ANEL (Cyprus)

Contact:

(email:) michelle.perello@consulta-europa.com

(website:) www.tourisme-project.eu

Deliverable Number: D5.1

Title of Deliverable: Report on the improvement in the uptake of sustainable solutions, growth and scaling up of tourism SMEs

Version of Deliverable: V1

Date of Submission of Deliverable: 15/05/2023

D5.1 Report on the improvement in the uptake of sustainable solutions, growth, and scaling up of tourism SMEs

WP5 Monitoring and evaluation of SMEs' sustainability improvement

TOURISME

Improving Sustainability of Tourism SMEs Through Knowledge Transfer, International Cooperation and Multi-Stakeholder Engagement

Co-funded by the COSME programme of the European Union

Improving sustainability of tourism SMEs through knowledge transfer, international cooperation and multi-stakeholder engagement

D5.1 – Report on the improvement in the uptake of sustainable solutions, growth and scaling up of tourism SMEs

Grant Agreement No	951103	Project Acronym	TOURISME
Project Title	Improving sustainability of tourism SMEs through knowledge transfer, international cooperation and multi-stakeholder engagement		
Deliverable No	D5.1		
Deliverable Full Title	Report on the improvement in the uptake of sustainable solutions, growth and scaling up of tourism SMEs		
Work Package No. and Title	WP5 - Monitoring and evaluation of SMEs' sustainability improvement		
Lead beneficiary	Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias, S.A.		
Authors	Lucía Dobarro Delgado, Teresa Rodríguez González, Pilar Guerra Rivero		
Contributors	Michelle Perello (CE); Beatrice Avagnina (CE); Alma Cruz (ITC); Francesco Lembo (ACR+); Erneszt Kóvacs (ACR+); Silvia Frau (RAS); Giorgia Farina (RAS); Ivana Russiello (SFC); Giuseppe Contu (SFC); Eleftherios Loizou (ANEL); Anna Andreou (ANEL)		
Planned delivery date	15/05/2023		
Actual delivery date	15/05/2023		
Dissemination level	Public		
Document version	V1		
Project start date	16 September 2020	Project duration	33
Document description	This report monitors the returns obtained from the adoption of innovative solutions and sustainable growth by SMEs compared to their initial situation.		

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	6
2. Setting up a monitoring system	8
2.1. Methodology	8
2.2 Monitoring and evaluation of SMEs' sustainability improvement	8
2.2.1. Environmental indicators	10
2.2.2. Social indicators	19
2.2.3. Economic indicators	23
3. Adoption of certifications	27
4. How the vision of business has changed.....	29
5. Best practices identified	30
6. Conclusions.....	1
List of figures.....	3
Annex 1: Monitoring system questionnaire	34

Abbreviations

KPI Key Performance Indicators

SME Small and Medium Enterprise

WP Work Package

D Deliverable

1. Introduction

Deliverable D5.1 Report on the improvement in the uptake of sustainable solutions, growth and scaling up of tourism SMEs was prepared in the context of Work Package 5 of the European Project – TOURISME: Improving the sustainability of tourism SMEs through knowledge transfer, international cooperation, and multi-stakeholder engagement.

Running in parallel with the scheme's implementation under WP4, WP5 deals with monitoring the performance of the developed schemes on the SME's uptake on innovative solutions and sustainable growth in comparison with their baseline scenario. More specifically the objectives have been:

- Build a monitoring system with specific indicators to measure SME's performance.
- Assess results and identify best performing SMEs.

This report addresses the improvement in the uptake of sustainable solutions, growth and scaling up of tourism SMEs in relation to the benchmark assessment performed in WP3. The report also describes the designed and implemented monitoring system.

Task 5.1. Setting up a monitoring system

Lead: SSSA; Participants: ITC, L'InstParisReg; Months: M11-12

This task aims at developing an integrated evaluation procedure to measure the performance and impacts of the implemented schemes in WP4. More specifically, it defines a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to environmental, social and economic impact categories associated to sustainable growth in the tourism sector. Examples of these indicators are resource efficiency, energy consumption, carbon emissions, social innovation, etc. These KPIs are part of a monitoring programme that envisages the methodologies and tools to be used for the evaluation of results (task 5.2) and necessary quantitative and qualitative data to perform the assessment.

Task 5.2 Monitoring SMEs' performance

Lead: ITC; Participants: CE, SSSA, L'InstParisReg, SFC, RAS, ANEL; Months: M13 - 24

During the entire implementation of the schemes, SMEs are followed-up and requested to provide data periodically by ITC and with support of CE, SSSA, L'InstParisReg, RAS, SFC and ANEL. An online template/tool was developed and distributed to SMEs, along with guidelines and tips to facilitate the process.

Task 5.3 Evaluation of results

Lead: ITC; Participants: CE, ACR+, SSSA, L'InstParisReg; Months: M25 -33

Data obtained through the indicated KPIs are analysed and contrasted with the benchmark data collected in WP3 with aims at assessing the performance of individual SMEs in comparison with their situation before the implementation of the schemes. Best performing SMEs are also identified to highlight best practices for potential replication from other European SMEs, which are included in the guidelines for sustainability in SMEs (task 6.4). Moreover, outcomes of Task 5.3 and D5.1 have fed.

2. Setting up a monitoring system

2.1. Methodology

In order to develop an evaluation procedure to measure the performance and impacts of the activities implemented by the TOURISME beneficiary companies, SSSA and ITC elaborated together a first questionnaire which takes into account a set of key indicators related to the environmental, social and economic impact categories. In addition, the certifications obtained by the companies were highlighted, both those that at the end of the project have a commitment to acquire them and those that have actually been certified. In June 2022 the questionnaire was sent to companies, and it was open until January 2023. The objective of this questionnaire is to assess the implementation of innovative and sustainable solutions by SMEs during the project compared to their initial situation in order to build a monitoring system for SMEs with specific indicators and to identify the best results and the good practices that have been implemented during the execution of the project.

2.2 Monitoring and evaluation of SMEs' sustainability improvement

Of the 65 beneficiary companies, 48 responded to the questionnaire of which 42% are travel agencies and 58% are accommodation. Of the total number of companies that responded to the questionnaire, 2 are from Cyprus, 16 from France, 14 from Italy and 16 from Spain (Figure 1,2)

N=48

Figure 1.1: Distribution of SME by countries

N=48

Figure 1.2: Distribution of SME by categories

2.2.1. Environmental indicators

Environmental indicators provide information on aspects such as energy conservation, water conservation, mobility, waste management and carbon footprint measures.

■ Energy conservation

With the data obtained from the survey we can confirm that 35.50% of the companies have implemented energy efficiency practices, 31.50% plan to implement them in the future and 31.5% do not plan to implement any measures in the near future (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Energy conservation involvement

Of the 35.50% that have implemented some practice related to energy saving are mostly hotels and other accommodation (27.08%), and to a lesser extent travel agencies and tour operators (10.42%). Among the measures implemented are the use of CFL and LED lighting, optimisation of kitchen operation, installation of light management control systems, key card systems and motion sensors in buildings, installation of solar panels (Figure 2.1). These data are an improvement on the initial data, where most of the companies had only implemented LEDs as a practice to reduce energy consumption (Figure 2.2).

N=33

Figure 2.2: Energy conservation initiatives

Water conservation

In relation to the implementation of water conservation initiatives, 56.25% of the companies have not implemented any action, 25% are planning to implement them and only 18.75% have implemented some action (Figure 3).

N=48

Figure 3.1: Water conservation

Compared to the initial situation where most of the companies only tried to reduce water consumption, we can conclude that companies have improved their water management by proposing new measures. Among the most implemented actions in hotels and similar accommodations are the optimisation of garden operations, optimisation of swimming pools, selection of native plants for gardens, optimisation of the laundry, greywater recycling, and installation of low-flush / dual-flush toilets (Figure 3.2)

N=21

Figure 3.2: Types of implemented actions for water management

Waste management

In terms of waste management, 50% of the companies have implemented practices related to waste management. 27.08% of companies plan to implement them in the future and 22.92% do not plan any initiatives in this respect in the near future.

Out of the 50% which have implemented practices, 33% are accommodation providers and 17% are travel agencies (Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: Waste management

The most common actions implemented by companies are the reduction of single-use plastic, waste sorting in rooms and offices, purchasing food according to customer demand, installation of composting machines (Figure 4.2).

N=37

Figure 4.2: Types of implemented actions for waste management

Sustainable mobility initiatives

Almost 50% of the companies have implemented measures related to sustainable mobility in the same percentage of accommodation and travel agencies, and 31,25% are planning to do so. Only 18,75% of the companies do not plan to implement any action (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1: Sustainable mobility initiatives

Among the actions implemented by both hotels and travel agencies, the promotion of sustainable transport among both employees and customers, in particular the use of public transport, bicycle rentals, etc., stands out. Among the accommodation companies, the installation of charging stations for electric vehicles stands out, and among the travel agencies, the promotion of more sustainable (Figure 5.2).

N=39

Figure 5.2: Types of sustainable mobility initiatives

Carbon footprint assessment

Only 8% of companies have carried out an assessment of the carbon footprint of their activity, 50% of companies are planning to do so and 42% have no plans to do so (Figure 6). In terms of carbon footprint measurement, a practice that very few companies are implementing, in fact, by the end of the project, only three companies had measured the carbon footprint of their activity, there is no difference with respect to the initial situation (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Carbon footprint assessment

Mitigation actions

16% of the companies have implemented mitigation actions, 30% plan to implement this measure but almost 50% of the companies do not have a concrete plan yet (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Mitigation actions

If we compare these results with the baseline data, we can highlight that it is still the accommodation companies that have implemented the most sustainable practices in their activities, but **we can also see an increase in the practices of travel agencies**, mainly on issues related to sustainable mobility and waste management, practices such as the promotion of the use of public transport and electric vehicles and the reduction of plastic waste.

At the beginning of the project 90% of the accommodation and travel agencies were motivated to implement sustainable practices and we can confirm that since the start of the project until the end most of these companies have started to implement some kind of sustainable practices.

2.2.2. Social indicators

■ Raise awareness and encourage behavioural changes on sustainability issues

75% of the companies have implemented practices aimed at raising awareness and changing habits related to reducing environmental impacts, 18.75% have planned to do so and only 6.25% do not express any intention (Figure 8.1).

Out of the 75% of companies that have implemented practices to raise awareness and change behaviours, 43.75% corresponds to accommodation and 31.25% to travel agencies.

Figure 8.1: Sustainability behavioural changes

Among the initiatives adopted by companies, travel agencies, hotels and accommodation companies agree on planning eco-friendly activities, raising customer awareness, training employees in sustainable practices, motivating customers to adopt sustainable practices (Figure 8.2).

Figure 8.2: Actions implemented to change sustainability behavioural.

Corporate Social Responsibility

52.08% of the companies have adopted initiatives related to Corporate Social Responsibility, of which 37,50% corresponds to accommodation and 14,58% to travel agencies, 20,83% of the companies plan to do so and 27,08% have no plans for the time being to address this initiative (Figure 9).

Figure 9.1: Involvement Social Corporate Responsibility by SMEs

The actions carried out by the accommodations are mainly focused on calculating the carbon footprint, food distribution among workers, furniture donations, motivating staff in times of crisis, and by the travel agencies the most important actions are to calculate the carbon footprint of each trip and offset it, planting trees and donations (Figure 9.1).

N=35

Figure 9.2: Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives

2.2.3. Economic indicators

■ Green procurement

52.08% of the companies have implemented green procurement practices, 35.42% of which are accommodations and 16.67% travel agencies.

As for the 25% of companies that plan to implement green procurement, 20.83% of them are accommodation companies and only 4.17% are travel agencies.

The majority of the companies that are not going to implement this measure are travel agencies, 20.83% compared to 2.08% of the accommodation companies (Figure 10.1).

Figure 10.1: Commitment to green procurement by SMEs

Among the measures adopted by the accommodations are purchasing from local suppliers, purchasing of 100% ecological material, use of ecological detergents, ecological purchasing of food and beverages, purchasing from local suppliers, and by the travel agencies the most outstanding actions are purchasing from local suppliers, ecological purchasing of food and beverages, and purchasing of reusable plastic bottles and glasses (Figure 10.2).

Figure 10.2: Green procurement initiatives

Sustainable policy

Of the almost half of the companies that have already implemented a sustainability management policy (47.92%), 33.33% are accommodation companies and 14.58% are travel agencies. On the other hand, 43.75% plan to implement sustainability policies in their companies compared to only 8.33% who do not plan to change their company's policy (Figure 11.1).

N=48

Figure 11.1: Implementation of sustainable policies by SMEs

The most common measures adopted by hotels and accommodations are the formulation of sustainability policies, promotion of sustainable travel, booking sustainable tourism activities, appointing an internal green team, and by travel agencies the implementation of policies that encourage sustainable travel packages, booking sustainable accommodations, formulating sustainable policies (Figure 11.2)

Figure 11.2: Sustainable policies adopted by SMEs.

3. Adoption of certifications

In relation to the acquisition of certificates, we can affirm that there has been an increase in the number of companies that are committed to or have acquired a certificate, 58% compared to the initial 14% (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Participation of SMEs in Sustainability Certificates

Companies that have achieved or are about to achieve certification have opted for the following certifications (Figure 12.1). Among the certifications most in demand by companies, Biosphere stands out, followed by Green Key, Ecolabel and Travel Life.

Figure 12.1: Sustainability Certificates achieved by SMEs.

If we compare this situation with the initial one of the 4 companies that were certified, these opted for ISO 140001/9001, ECOLABEL, Legambiente Turismo and Travel Life (figure 12.2).

Figure 12.2: Sustainability Certificates initially achieved by SMEs.

Finally, we would like to highlight those companies that have not yet made a commitment but that are in the process of obtaining the following certificates.

- Biosphere
- ISO 9001
- ISO 140001
- Passivhaus
- Tourcert
- Earthcheck

4. How the vision of business has changed

Having analysed the final statistics and surveys, we can conclude that most companies have changed their vision when committing to sustainability.

They have stated that they are more aware of what sustainability means and have conveyed this to their employees and customers.

On the other hand, they are also more aware of the importance of adapting to a new customer who is more aware of sustainability and who is looking for a different way of doing tourism.

Below are some of the comments from the companies on their new vision after participating in the project:

- **Canary Hospitality**, “We have not changed the vision we had originally, this project has helped us to broaden it in the sense of knowing new areas and challenges related to the transformation of the industry into a sustainable model”.
- **Alba Hotels**, “It is essential for us to share a common vision with our guests and staff. Participating in the tourism project reinforced our desire to always do more, especially in terms of communication. We talked about green communication and how important it is to let people know about the actions we carry out”.
- **Ecotourism o rincón**, “Our vision changed completely, learning from other sustainable tourism destinations in **order** to improve in our organisation several changes, among them the collaboration with public entities”.
- **Hotel Duo**, “Every staff member and many guests are participating in our sustainable programme by **minimising** the use of plastic, reusing towels and not asking for the room to be cleaned every day”.
- **Hotel Santa Gilla**, “After the Tourisme project, we realised the quality of eco-sustainable practices and how they serve the dual purpose of helping the environment in which we live and **responding** to the new needs of travellers in this decade, and we foresee a development of the accommodation facility that must provide complete sustainability, environmental, economic and social”.

5. Best practices identified

By the end of the TOURISME project, we can confirm that the SME beneficiaries have already started to implement good practices on sustainability. Some of them were easier to incorporate without the need for large investments and others will be implemented in the medium- and long-term strategic planning. Many of these practices have been learned through the training courses, as well as by the exchanges that took place among the participants, taking as a reference those with higher level in terms of implementing sustainable measures. In this sense, the SMEs could identify themselves in the Madrid 2023 workshop (WP4) as “seeds”, in a starting point of sustainability, “flowers”, having the initial results on sustainability measures and “fruits”, in an advance level of implementation.

Among the good practices that we have identified within the hotels and other accommodations, the following stand out:

- Formulation of a **sustainability** policy as part of the certification process.
- Introduction of tablets in the rooms and at the reception to display menus and avoid printing on paper.
- Introduction of Eco-tariffs for rooms - the guest pays 5 euros less for his room and we do not do the service during his stay (minimum stay - 3 nights)
- Implementation of circular economy such as composting as a way to dispose of organic waste, no use of plastics, recycling of glass bottles for amenities, organic food and drink, eco certified cleaning products.
- Organic breakfast offer.
- Communication of the company's philosophy in terms of sustainability to employees and customers, establishing an eco-responsibility statement, inclusion of sustainability in the job description, installation of aerators on taps and showers to reduce water consumption.
- Reorganisation of meals as they are the source of waste.
- Raising awareness of respect and protection of the biodiversity of the environment among customers.
- Measuring the carbon footprint as a sustainability indicator to measure, evaluate and monitor the impact of the company's activity.
- Improve communication to attract committed customers, who seek sustainable experiences and who take into account the impact of their actions and the services they contract.
- Implementation of practices to control energy and water consumption.
- Training employees in sustainability practices as making changes to internal processes will make the company more efficient and achieve its sustainability goals.
- Through CSR policy and Responsible Purchasing policy, encouraging short circuits and responsible consumption (redistribution of food).
- Implementation of energy efficiency practices, and Development of short circuits and responsible consumption (food redistribution).

- Implementation of practices to change cleaning products, using eco-labels to provide information to employees and customers about the company's green purchasing policy.
- Awareness raising and training of people in positions of responsibility to enable them to make effective decisions in the transition to a more sustainable management model.

Among the travel agencies and tour operators we highlight the following best practices:

- Establishment of a network of suppliers with sustainable criteria from both a social and environmental point of view.
- Sharing best practices with customers through workshops.
- Offer responsible tourism magazines to customers.
- Promote green marketing.
- Promote sustainable mobility through public transport and walking tours.
- Develop a range of low environmental impact tourist circuits that not only attract a more aware clientele but also offer a new proposal to traditional customers.
- Suggest to customers to offset carbon emissions through the financing of climate reduction and regeneration projects.
- Offer vegetarian options for meals.
- Encourage the use of the train for travel wherever possible.
- If air travel is necessary, they should have as few connections as possible.
- Concentrate on shorter journeys to neighbouring countries 100% accessible by train.
- Promote long-stay trips, especially if air travel is unavoidable.
- Development of the offer of public transport and tourist cards for both buses and trains and promotion of guided tours on foot.
- Promotion of night trains.
- Development of a genuine "Signature Experience" offer.
- Establishment of a charter for responsible travel.
- Development of a sustainable and responsible travel offer.
- Develop a letter for partners that respects the company's sustainability policy.
- Develop content on the company's web pages with themes that highlight the values of sustainable and responsible tourism adopted by the company.
- Establish an internal charter on the daily activities of the company such as email, supplies, incidents with customers, furniture and so on.

6. Conclusions

After analysing the statistics and SME feedback, we can conclude that companies have increased their commitment to sustainability, mainly because they are now aware that sustainability is not only related to the environmental impacts of their activities, but that they have a broader view of the concept of sustainability, such as the social and economic aspect of sustainability.

With regard to the methodology and the results obtained, it was a great effort to involve all the companies in this analysis, given that of the 65 companies participating in the project, we only obtained information from 48 SMEs, which is why we asked for additional information from the partners of these companies that did not answer the questionnaire.

In the analysis of the results of the environmental indicators, we can conclude that an increase of measures applied mainly by hotels and other accommodation compared to travel agencies and tour operators has been identified, this statement has its logic in the type of activity and the different infrastructures of the companies. Some initiatives identified by the companies were not initially considered because the companies were not aware that they were measures that could be considered sustainable, other initiatives were easily incorporated because they did not represent a major challenge for the companies, but they were not considered as sustainable measures.

Regarding the analysis of social indicators, as mentioned earlier, many companies did not consider this type of activity within the framework of sustainability, which is why we can identify an increase in measures implemented, both by hotels and other accommodations, and by travel agencies and tour operators and because many of these initiatives do not involve a large expense for SMEs.

Regarding the measurement of the carbon footprint, few companies have dedicated the means and the time to achieve it, the conclusion we reached is that since the majority have dedicated their efforts to acquire environmental certifications, along the way they will obtain the same benefits and cost savings opportunities linked to electricity and fuel consumption, improving its images, complying with regulations and being more competitive in the market.

Regarding the economic indicators, although many companies already considered green purchases initially, they only took into account the ecological value of the purchased product. After the training courses, they are aware that not only direct purchase is related to sustainability, but also the way in which these products are produced. Now they take more into account that suppliers also share their same values in sustainability.

Another important indicator is the establishment of a business strategy in the medium and long term. We can confirm that the workshop that we carried out in the matchmaking of Madrid 2023 convinced the majority of the companies that they should have a company policy where the commitment to reduce the impacts of their activity is established and key decisions are made taking into account all factors related to sustainability.

In terms of environmental and sustainability certifications, we can confirm that it has been a success that most companies have acquired the commitment to become certified and have even managed to become certified

in a short space of time, in addition to the effort made, given the complexity of most of the certificates. The certification process allows the company to work on a guide of actions that they must adopt, which makes it easier for them to make a medium and long-term strategic plan and on the other hand, no less important, it is a way of communicating the company's philosophy in terms of sustainability externally. Although many companies at the beginning of the project already knew what type of certification they were going to achieve, most have chosen to be certified with companies that participated in one of the trainings and were able to explain to them face to face the characteristics of the certificates, a clear example is the from Biosphere certificate.

Finally, the exchange of knowledge and experiences by all the companies benefiting from the project has been highly valued, as they have been able to create a team and to work together on a common strategy to begin to make a difference in terms of sustainability in the short and medium term. In this sense, we must emphasize that several companies have come to establish relationships between them.

List of figures

Figure 1.1: Distribution of SME by countries.....	9
Figure 1.2: Distribution of SME by categories.....	9
Figure 2.1: Energy conservation involvement.....	10
Figure 2.2: Energy conservation initiatives	11
Figure 3.1: Water conservation	12
Figure 3.2: Types of implemented actions for water management.....	13
Figure 4.1: Waste management	14
Figure 4.2: Types of implemented actions for waste management	15
Figure 5.1: Sustainable mobility initiatives	16
Figure 5.2: Types of sustainable mobility initiatives	17
Figure 6: Carbon footprint assessment.....	18
Figure 7: Mitigation actions	18
Figure 8.1: Sustainability behavioural changes	19
Figure 8.2: Actions implemented to change sustainability behavioural.	20
Figure 9.1: Involvement Social Corporate Responsibility by SMEs.....	21
Figure 9.2: Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives	22
Figure 10.1: Commitment to green procurement by SMEs	23
Figure 10.2: Green procurement initiatives.....	24
Figure 11.1: Implementation of sustainable policies by SMEs	25
Figure 11.2: Sustainable policies adopted by SMEs.....	26
Figure 12: Participation of SMEs in Sustainability Certificates	27
Figure 12.1: Sustainability Certificates achieved by SMEs.	27
Figure 12.2: Sustainability Certificates initially achieved by SMEs.....	28

Annex 1: Monitoring system questionnaire

Impact category	N°	KPI - Question	Metric
Environment	1	Have you implemented a monitoring system of your organisation's energy consumption in the last two years?	1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented
Environment	2	Have you implemented practices directly related to energy conservation in your organisation in the last two year?	1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented
Environment	3	Energy conservation practices	1- Number of energy conservation practices implemented/year 2- Total solar panels installed 3- Number of smart thermostats/Total thermostats 4-Number of energy efficient lights (e.g.CFL, LED)/Total lights
Environment	4	Have you implemented a monitoring system of your organisation's water consumption in the last two years?	1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented

Environment	5	Have you implemented practices directly related to water conservation in your organisation in the last two year?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented
Environment	6	Water recycling practices	Number of water recycling practices implemented/ year
Environment	7	Water conservation practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Number of water conservation practices implemented/year 2- Number of native plants selected for gardens/ Total plants 3- Number of water consumption monitoring sensors installed /year
Environment	8	Have you implemented waste monitoring system in your organisation in the last two years?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented
Environment	9	Have you implemented waste recycling practices in your organisation in the last two years?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented

Environment	10	Waste recycling practices	1- Number of waste recycling practices implemented/year 2- Total number of waste fractions collected separately
Environment	11	Reducing food waste	Number of food donations/year
Social	12	Have you implemented staff training on sustainability issues in your organisation in the last two years?	1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented
Social	13	Training staff on sustainability topics	Number of training hours per employee related to sustainability topics / Total of training hours
Social	14	Have you implemented awareness-raising practices on sustainability issues in your organisation in the last two years?	1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented

Social	15	Raising awareness on sustainability issues	Number of sustainability-related information and education campaigns for visitors or employees/ Year
Economic	16	Have you implemented green procurement practices in your organisation in the last two years?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented
Social	17	Community engagement	Number of local suppliers /Total suppliers
Environment	18	Green procurement - Suppliers	Number of suppliers selected according to environmental criteria/Total suppliers
Economic	19	Green procurement	Number of purchases made according to environmental criteria/Year

Economic	20	Green procurement - technological solutions to improve consumption efficiency	Investment in technological solutions to improve consumption efficiency € /year
Environment, Social, Economic	21	Have you implemented a sustainable policy or management in your organisation in the last two years?	1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented
Environment	22	Have you implemented eco-mobility initiatives in the last two years?	1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented
Environment	23	Have you implemented a carbon footprint assessment of your organisation in the last two years?	1 -Strongly implemented 2- Implemented 3- Stable 4- Poorly implemented 5-Not implemented
Environment	24	Have you adopted any certifications or ecolabels in your organization in the last two years? (please specify)	1- Yes 2- No

	25	<p>If yes, please specify the type of certification or ecolab</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-ISO 9001 2-ISO 14001 3-ISO 22000 4-ISO 50001 5-ISO 45001/OHSAS 18001 6-EMAS 7-EU Ecolabel 8-Green Globe 9-Green Key 10-Nordic Swan 11-Blue Angel 12-NF Environment 13-ECORISMO 14-Legambiente Turismo 15-BIO HOTELS d'Italia 16-AENOR Medio Ambiente/AENOR Residuo Cero 17-HES - Hoteles Eficientes Sostenibles
<p>Environment, Social, Economic</p>	26	<p>Could you briefly describe how you envisage sustainable tourism in your organisation? How has your vision changed in the last two years?</p>	

The content of this publication represents the views of the author only and is his/her sole responsibility; it cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission and/or the Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME) or any other body of the European Union. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.

TOURISME

Improving Sustainability of Tourism SMEs Through Knowledge Transfer, International Cooperation and Multi-Stakeholder Engagement

Co-funded by the COSME programme of the European Union

